

*Heuristic Variational Analysis of the Single-Slice Feynman Path Integral:
Conceptual Insights into Short-Time Propagation*

Abstract

This work investigates a variational perspective on the Feynman path integral, aiming to explore connections between stationary action, probability amplitude, integrating over *path evolutions*, and the semiclassical limit. The variational analysis employed should be viewed as *conceptually explorative and heuristic rather than strictly formal*. It explores how variations of path evolutions in the path integral at the level of a single infinitesimal slice can yield meaningful insight into the behavior of quantum trajectories. A local variational analysis of the free particle and a particle near a constant potential provides insight into how the stationary-action principle underlies both classical and quantum behavior, through a local relationship between the classical slice-action and a functional over the phase-weighting of quantum path evolutions. In particular, this functional is proportional to the slice-action itself up to additive and multiplicative constants. This proportionality implies that the stationarity of this functional is equivalent to the stationarity of the slice-action, which in turn generates the semiclassical stationary path evolution. The resulting formulation produces results consistent with known short-time propagators for the free particle and a particle near a constant potential, including tunneling behavior.

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The Feynman Propagator

Starting with the well-known Feynman propagator in heuristic form (Feynman & Hibbs, Chapter 2-4), written in the position basis, summing up all probability amplitude to go from $|x(0)\rangle$ to $|x'(t)\rangle$:

$$K(x'(t), t; x(0), 0) = \langle x' | e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} \hat{H} t} | x(0) \rangle = \int_{x(0)}^{x'(t)} D[x(\tau)] e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} \int_0^t L(t, x, \dot{x}) d\tau} = \int_{x(0)}^{x'(t)} D[x(\tau)] e^{\frac{i}{\hbar} S[0, t]} \quad (1)$$

In a more rigorous form, the Feynman propagator $K(x'(t), t; x(0), 0)$ can be defined as its time-sliced Gaussian construction (Feynman & Hibbs, Chapters 2-4&3-1; Schulman, Chapters 1&6):

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{m}{2\pi i \hbar \Delta t} \right)^{\frac{N}{2}} \int dx_{N-1} \cdots \int dx_1 e^{\frac{i \Delta t}{\hbar} \left[\frac{1}{2} m \frac{(x_1 - x_0)^2}{\Delta t^2} - V(x_0) \right]} \cdots e^{\frac{i \Delta t}{\hbar} \left[\frac{1}{2} m \frac{(x_N - x_{N-1})^2}{\Delta t^2} - V(x_{N-1}) \right]} \quad (2)$$

In which all integrals are to be taken over the entire real line. Although the real-time form of this expression is oscillatory and not convergent in the usual sense, the time-sliced Gaussian construction yields finite, well-defined results for important examples such as the free particle and the quantum harmonic oscillator (Feynman & Hibbs, Chapters 3-1&3-6), after proper limiting procedures (e.g., recursive evaluation or Wick rotation).

Path evolutions

The goal of this article is to explore the possibility of deriving some meaningful insight from varying a single slice of the Feynman propagator (1). In the case of the free particle the potential terms in (2) are zero:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{m}{2\pi i \hbar \Delta t} \right)^{\frac{N}{2}} \int dx_{N-1} \cdots \int dx_1 e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{\hbar} \left[\frac{1}{2} m \frac{(x_1 - x_0)^2}{\Delta t^2} \right]} \dots e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{\hbar} \left[\frac{1}{2} m \frac{(x_N - x_{N-1})^2}{\Delta t^2} \right]} \quad (3)$$

When computing this expression, integrating over the trajectories partitioned into N time-slices, one encounters Gaussian integrals consisting of two terms for each integration variable, e.g. for dx_1 :

$$\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i \hbar \Delta t} \right)^{2/2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_1 e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{\hbar} \left[\frac{1}{2} m \left\{ \frac{(x_2 - x_1)^2}{\Delta t^2} + \frac{(x_1 - x_0)^2}{\Delta t^2} \right\} \right]} \quad (4)$$

In which the variable over which is integrated represents the infinite paths a particle can take from x_0 to x_1 , and from x_1 to x_2 , by allowing x_1 to assume all possible values. This integral can be evaluated to a form that can be recursively absorbed into the integral over dx_2 , also consisting of two such terms, etc., ultimately producing a finite value in the limit for $N \rightarrow \infty$. However, the goal is not to calculate this finite value of total probability amplitude, which is known (Feynman & Hibbs, Chapter 3-1), but to derive conceptual insight from the path integral by considering *path evolutions*. To this purpose, starting with this first-slice integral, which by the substitutions:

$$\dot{x} = \frac{(x_2 - x_1)}{\Delta t}, \text{ and } x_1 - x_0 = (x_2 - x_0) - (x_2 - x_1)$$

can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{m}{2\pi i \hbar \Delta t} \right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} -\Delta t d\dot{x} e^{\frac{im\Delta t}{2\hbar} \left[\dot{x}^2 + \frac{((x_2 - x_0) - (x_2 - x_1))^2}{\Delta t^2} \right]} = \\ & \left(\frac{m}{2\pi i \hbar \Delta t} \right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} -\Delta t d\dot{x} e^{\frac{im\Delta t}{2\hbar} \left[2\dot{x}^2 + \frac{4(x_2 - x_0)^2}{4\Delta t^2} - \frac{4(x_2 - x_0)(x_2 - x_1)}{2\Delta t^2} \right]} = \\ & \left(\frac{m}{2\pi i \hbar} \right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} -d\dot{x} e^{\frac{im\Delta t}{2\hbar} [2\dot{x}^2 - 4v\dot{x} + 4v^2]} \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

In which the constant ratio $\frac{(x_2-x_0)}{2\Delta t}$ is taken as a constant average velocity v , as in this integral Δt and the points x_0 and x_2 do not vary. The integral over all paths between these points has now been written as an integral over all *path evolutions* between these points.

In line with the path-integral formalism, we write the integral (5) in terms of the Lagrangian $L = m\dot{x}^2 - 2mv\dot{x} + 2mv^2$ between beginning and end points of the first discretized slice:

$$\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} -d\dot{x} e^{\frac{im\Delta t}{2\hbar}[2\dot{x}^2 - 4v\dot{x} + 4v^2]} = \left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} -d\dot{x} e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}\Delta t L(\dot{x})} \quad (6)$$

Variational calculus on the first slice

We now wish to probe this slice of the path integral to investigate whether local Euler-Lagrange stationary path evolutions can be found. We do so by applying variational calculus for two physical situations of the motion from x_0 to x_2 : *without* a potential (free particle motion) and *with* a (constant) potential. We do so in the limit of sufficiently small Δt , which is legitimate as we can make the first slice arbitrarily small.

Variational analysis of the free particle

Regarding the integrand of (6) as that of a functional with time as independent variable:

$$F(\dot{x}) \equiv -e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}\Delta t L(\dot{x})} \quad (7)$$

Up to first order in small Δt , through the exponential, we may Taylor-expand (7) into:

$$F = -\left(1 + i\frac{\Delta t L}{\hbar}\right) = -1 - i\frac{\Delta t L}{\hbar} \quad (8)$$

To first order approximation for small Δt , the integral of a function $f(t)$ with respect to time is:

$$\int_t^{t+\Delta t} f(t') dt' = f(t)\Delta t$$

Again to first order approximation, taking the derivative with respect to time amounts to dividing by Δt again:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\int_t^{t+\Delta t} f(t') dt' \right) = f(t)$$

For sufficiently small, finite Δt , integrating (8) from t to $t + \Delta t$:

$$\int_t^{t+\Delta t} F dt = F\Delta t = -\Delta t - i \frac{\Delta t^2 L}{\hbar} = -\Delta t - \frac{i}{\hbar} \Delta t L \Delta t \quad (9)$$

The action will still be stationary over this interval:

$$S = \int_t^{t+\Delta t} L dt = L\Delta t \quad (10)$$

For sufficiently small Δt , the functional (9) is thus some constant plus some other constant times the action over Δt , and therefore it must also be stationary over Δt :

$$\int_t^{t+\Delta t} F dt = F\Delta t = -\Delta t - \frac{i}{\hbar} \Delta t L \Delta t = -\Delta t - \frac{i}{\hbar} \Delta t S \quad (11)$$

For sufficiently small Δt , the Euler-Lagrange equation for this functional is then:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) - \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} = 0 \rightarrow \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) = 0 \quad (12)$$

Meaning that $\frac{\partial F}{\partial \dot{x}}$ is a constant, because F has translational symmetry. Working out these conditions up to first order in Δt :

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \dot{x}} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \dot{x}} \left(1 + i \frac{\Delta t L}{\hbar} \right) = -i \frac{\Delta t}{\hbar} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} = -2i \frac{m\Delta t}{\hbar} (\dot{x} - v) \quad (13)$$

The total time derivative is in general not equal to the partial derivative with respect to t , but for Δt sufficiently small we may assume any particular \dot{x} to be constant over a single slice. As there are no higher derivatives of x in L and thus also not in F , the $\frac{d}{dt}$ is then equal to $\frac{\partial}{\partial t}$. For sufficiently small Δt , this approximation should hold, and the Euler-Lagrange equation (12) generates the semiclassical stationary-path evolution $\dot{x} = v$, which is the physically meaningful evolution without including any potential. Up to zeroth order in Δt :

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) = -2i \frac{m}{\hbar} (\dot{x} - v) = 0 \rightarrow \dot{x} = v \quad (14)$$

This should be interpreted in light of the oscillatory nature of the path integral. The stationarity of the action corresponds to a stationary phase of $e^{i\frac{S}{\hbar}}$, so that in the semiclassical limit, where the action is large compared to \hbar , the integral is dominated by trajectories satisfying the classical equations of motion. The stationary-phase approximation therefore provides the mathematical justification for why stationary paths contribute most significantly, and how quantum propagation transitions smoothly to the classical regime in this formulation. In the semiclassical limit, stationary phase corresponds to conservation of momentum (14).

Calculating the contribution of the stationary path evolution (14) to the total probability amplitude for the first slice, by varying the path evolution with small fluctuations in velocity (ε):

$$\dot{x} = v + \varepsilon \rightarrow \frac{d\dot{x}}{d\varepsilon} = 1$$

Substituting this into $-\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i \hbar}\right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\dot{x} e^{\frac{im\Delta t}{2\hbar}[2\dot{x}^2 - 4v\dot{x} + 4v^2]}$ (6) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} & -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i \hbar}\right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{im\Delta t}{2\hbar}[2(v+\varepsilon)^2 - 4v(v+\varepsilon) + 4v^2]} \\ &= -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i \hbar}\right) e^{\frac{i\Delta t m v^2}{\hbar}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar}\varepsilon^2} \\ &= \left(\frac{m}{2\pi \hbar}\right) e^{\frac{i\Delta t m v^2}{\hbar}} \sqrt{\frac{\pi \hbar}{m\Delta t}} e^{-i\pi/4} e^{i\pi/2} \\ &= \left(\frac{m}{2\pi \hbar}\right) \sqrt{\frac{\pi \hbar}{m\Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{\frac{i\Delta t m v^2}{\hbar}} = \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi \hbar \Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{\frac{i\Delta t m v^2}{\hbar}} \\ & K_{Free}(x_2, 2\Delta t; x_0, 0) \equiv \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi \hbar \Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{\frac{i\Delta t m v^2}{\hbar}} \quad (15) \end{aligned}$$

The latter (15) is the contribution to the full propagator (total probability amplitude) from the first slice for a free particle, consistent (up to some phase-factor) with the free-particle short-time propagator in Feynman & Hibbs, Chapter 3-1. The magnitude of the probability amplitude (15) squared, multiplied with the slice-length $(x_2 - x_0)$, gives the approximate probability of observing the particle in between x_0 and x_2 :

$$P(x_0, x_2) \approx \frac{m}{4\pi\hbar\Delta t} \cdot (x_2 - x_0) = \frac{m\Delta x}{2\pi\hbar 2\Delta t} \quad (16)$$

In (16) $2\Delta t$ is the duration of the first slice, so that in the limit of $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, $P(x_0, x_0 + dx) \rightarrow \frac{p}{2\pi\hbar}$ with p the momentum associated with the stationary-path evolution. This is consistent with the well-known result for the free particle: $P(x, x + dx) = \frac{m}{2\pi\hbar(t_b - t_a)} dx$, if we identify $(t_b - t_a)$ with the duration of the first slice and dx with the slice-length (Feynman & Hibbs, Chapter 3-1).

Variational analysis of a particle obstructed by a constant potential

Adding a constant potential V to the Lagrangian from (6) between x_0 and x_2 gives:

$$L = m\dot{x}^2 - 2mv\dot{x} + 2mv^2 - V \quad (17)$$

We wish to know for which \dot{x} the energy of the motion is equal to the potential energy. Solving the resulting quadratic in \dot{x} gives:

$$m\dot{x}^2 - 2mv\dot{x} + 2mv^2 - V = 0$$

$$\dot{x}^2 - 2v\dot{x} + 2v^2 - V/m = 0$$

$$\dot{x} = v \pm \sqrt{\frac{V - mv^2}{m}} \quad (18)$$

From (17) we clearly see that there are two physical situations, from the roots of the Lagrangian (18). Either the particle's kinetic energy is greater than or equal to the potential ($V \leq mv^2$): free particle motion in between x_0 and x_2 . Or it is less than the potential ($V > mv^2$): forbidden particle motion in between x_0 and x_2 , and the particle must tunnel through the potential in order to arrive from x_0 at x_2 .

The Euler-Lagrange equation (14) does not give any extra information for a constant potential added to the Lagrangian. To derive a Euler-Lagrange equation that does, we also incorporate the second-order term in the expansion of the exponential in (7):

$$F(\dot{x}) \equiv -e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}\Delta t L(\dot{x})}$$

Up to second order in Δt :

$$F = - \left(1 + \frac{i\Delta t L}{\hbar} - \frac{\Delta t^2 L^2}{2\hbar^2} \right) \quad (19)$$

The second-order expansion (19) of the functional (7) is also stationary on $[t, t + \Delta t]$ by virtue of stationarity of the action, based on similar arguments as for (11). That is, higher-order expansions are formed by terms of higher powers of the action. A stationary functional (i.e. the action) exponentiated to some power, scaled by a constant and shifted by another constant, is still a stationary functional (Gelfand & Fomin, §1.4–1.5). For the same stationary path as the action itself, although the nature of the stationary path (minimum or maximum) may change. The same holds for a sum of such stationary terms. Performing a similarly local Euler-Lagrange procedure as for (11) on this basis:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial F}{\partial \dot{x}} &= - \frac{\partial}{\partial \dot{x}} \left(1 + \frac{i\Delta t L}{\hbar} - \frac{\Delta t^2 L^2}{2\hbar^2} \right) \\ &= - \left(\frac{i\Delta t}{\hbar} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} - \frac{2\Delta t^2 L}{2\hbar^2} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) \\ &= - \left(\frac{i\Delta t}{\hbar} - \frac{\Delta t^2 L}{\hbar^2} \right) \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ &= - \frac{\Delta t}{\hbar} \left(i - \frac{L\Delta t}{\hbar} \right) \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} \\ &= - \frac{2m\Delta t}{\hbar} \left(i - \frac{L\Delta t}{\hbar} \right) (\dot{x} - v) \quad (20) \end{aligned}$$

Up to first order in Δt , using the same approximation as for Euler-Lagrange equation (14):

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) = - \frac{2m}{\hbar} \left(i - \frac{L\Delta t}{\hbar} \right) (\dot{x} - v) \quad (21)$$

As the potential V is a constant, L and thus F do not explicitly depend on x :

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) - \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} = 0 \rightarrow \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) = 0 \quad (22)$$

This gives for the stationary path evolutions, from (21) and (22), up to first order in Δt :

$$-\frac{2m}{\hbar} \left(i - \frac{L\Delta t}{\hbar} \right) (\dot{x} - v) = 0 \quad (23)$$

The interpretation of allowable stationary path evolutions now seems clear from (23). A real root $\dot{x} = v$ corresponds to the situation $V \leq mv^2$ from (18): free particle motion in between x_0 and x_2 . The other (complex) roots correspond to the situation $V > mv^2$ from (18): forbidden particle motion in between x_0 and x_2 , and the particle must tunnel through the potential in order to arrive from x_0 at x_2 .

The factor $\left(i - \frac{L\Delta t}{\hbar} \right) = 0$ implies that:

$$L\Delta t = i\hbar \rightarrow S = i\hbar \quad (24)$$

The imaginary action in (24) clearly signifies classically forbidden behavior and regions of evanescence (vanishing probability density), in this case in between x_0 and x_2 , and the particle must tunnel through the potential to get to x_2 . Setting the factor $\left(i - \frac{L\Delta t}{\hbar} \right) = 0$ and substituting the Lagrangian (17) into it gives:

$$\begin{aligned} L = \frac{i\hbar}{\Delta t} &\rightarrow m\dot{x}^2 - 2mv\dot{x} + 2mv^2 - V = \frac{i\hbar}{\Delta t} \\ m\dot{x}^2 - 2mv\dot{x} + 2mv^2 - \left(V + \frac{i\hbar}{\Delta t} \right) &= 0 \\ \dot{x}^2 - 2v\dot{x} + 2v^2 - \left(\frac{V}{m} + \frac{i\hbar}{m\Delta t} \right) &= 0 \quad (25) \end{aligned}$$

Giving the following two solutions for stationary path evolutions:

$$\dot{x}_{\pm} = v \pm \sqrt{\frac{V}{m} + \frac{i\hbar}{m\Delta t} - v^2} \quad (26)$$

$$(\dot{x}_{\pm} - v)^2 = \left(\frac{V}{m} + \frac{i\hbar}{m\Delta t} - v^2 \right) \quad (27)$$

To calculate the contribution of these complex-valued stationary path evolutions to the total probability amplitude, a bit more work is required. Starting again by varying the path evolution \dot{x}_{\pm} with small fluctuations in velocity (ε):

$$\dot{x} = \dot{x}_{\pm} + \varepsilon \rightarrow \frac{d\dot{x}}{d\varepsilon} = 1$$

For the case of the constant potential, the contribution from the first slice to the full propagator (total probability amplitude) from x_0 to x_2 is:

$$-\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{\hbar}L(x)} \quad (28)$$

$$L(x) = m\dot{x}^2 - 2mv\dot{x} + 2mv^2 - V \quad (29)$$

Up to second order in ε , any sufficiently smooth Lagrangian, Taylor-expanded about \dot{x}_{\pm} is:

$$L(\dot{x}_{\pm} + \varepsilon) = L(\dot{x}_{\pm}) + L'(\dot{x}_{\pm})\varepsilon + L''(\dot{x}_{\pm})\frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \quad (30)$$

Which gives the following for the Lagrangian (29):

$$L(\dot{x}_{\pm} + \varepsilon) = \frac{i\hbar}{\Delta t} + 2m(\dot{x}_{\pm} - v)\varepsilon + 2m\frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \quad (31)$$

Substituting $L(\dot{x}) = L(\dot{x}_{\pm} + \varepsilon)$ into $-\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{\hbar}L(x)}$ gives, up to second order in ε :

$$-\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{\hbar}L(\dot{x}_{\pm} + \varepsilon)} = -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{\hbar}L(\dot{x}_{\pm})} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{2\hbar}(2L'(\dot{x}_{\pm})\varepsilon + L''(\dot{x}_{\pm})\varepsilon^2)}$$

$L(\dot{x}_{\pm})$ are precisely the roots of (25), giving $L(\dot{x}_{\pm}) = \frac{i\hbar}{\Delta t}$:

$$\begin{aligned} & -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{\hbar}L(\dot{x}_{\pm})} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{2\hbar}L''(\dot{x}_{\pm})\left(\varepsilon + \frac{L'(\dot{x}_{\pm})}{L''(\dot{x}_{\pm})}\right)^2 - \frac{i\Delta t}{2\hbar} \frac{(L'(\dot{x}_{\pm}))^2}{L''(\dot{x}_{\pm})}} \\ & = -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) e^{-1} e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{2\hbar} \frac{(L'(\dot{x}_{\pm}))^2}{L''(\dot{x}_{\pm})}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{2\hbar}L''(\dot{x}_{\pm})\left(\varepsilon + \frac{L'(\dot{x}_{\pm})}{L''(\dot{x}_{\pm})}\right)^2} \quad (32) \end{aligned}$$

From (29) we see that $L''(\dot{x}_{\pm}) = 2m$ (constant) and that only $L'(\dot{x}_{\pm}) = 2m(\dot{x}_{\pm} - v)$ has different values for the positive and negative roots.

Rewriting (26) in the following way:

$$(\dot{x}_{\pm} - v) \equiv \pm r$$

This gives, upon substitution in (32):

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) e^{-1} e^{-\frac{i\Delta t(2mr)^2}{2\hbar}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{2\hbar} 2m\left(\varepsilon + \frac{\pm 2mr}{2m}\right)^2} \\
& = -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) e^{-1} e^{-\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar} r^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar} (\varepsilon \pm r)^2} \quad (33)
\end{aligned}$$

With one last transformation of integration variable $\delta = \varepsilon \pm r$ in (33) yielding:

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) e^{-1} e^{-\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar} r^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\delta e^{\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar} \delta^2} \\
& = \left(\frac{m}{2\pi\hbar}\right) e^{-1} e^{-\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar} r^2} \sqrt{\frac{\pi\hbar}{m\Delta t}} e^{-i\pi/4} e^{i\pi/2} \\
& = \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi\hbar\Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{-1} e^{-\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar} r^2} \\
& = \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi\hbar\Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{-1} e^{-\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar} \left(\frac{V}{m} + \frac{i\hbar}{m\Delta t} - v^2\right)} \\
& = \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi\hbar\Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{-1} e^1 e^{-\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar} \left(\frac{V}{m} - v^2\right)} \\
& = \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi\hbar\Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{-\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar} \left(\frac{V}{m} - v^2\right)} \quad (34)
\end{aligned}$$

The obtained first-slice contribution (34) to the full propagator is consistent with results from many standard textbooks (e.g., Landau & Lifshitz, §8; Schulman, Chapter 2): a constant phase-factor for the constant potential (K_V), multiplied with (15), the free contribution (K_{Free}):

$$K_V \cdot K_{Free}(x_2, 2\Delta t; x_0, 0) = e^{-\frac{i\Delta t}{\hbar} V} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi\hbar\Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{\frac{i\Delta t m v^2}{\hbar}} \quad (35)$$

This is what we obtain for the first-slice contribution to the full propagator (total probability amplitude) when we impose only the first factor $\left(i - \frac{L\Delta t}{\hbar}\right)$ in (23) to be zero:

$$-\frac{2m}{\hbar} \left(i - \frac{L\Delta t}{\hbar}\right) (\dot{x} - v) = 0$$

We did not obtain damping in the first-slice contribution to the total probability amplitude (34); clearly, we must do more to do so. If we also demand the second factor $(\dot{x} - v)$ of (23) to be zero, we see that this is equivalent to demanding that $\frac{dL}{d\dot{x}} = 0$:

$$\frac{dL}{d\dot{x}} = 2m\dot{x} - 2mv = 2m(\dot{x} - v) = 0 \leftrightarrow (\dot{x} - v) = 0 \leftrightarrow \dot{x} = v$$

But now v is no longer a real quantity, as for the free particle, but complex-valued. If we impose that $L'(\dot{x}_{\pm}) = 0$ in (30), (31) and (32), then the linear term in ε disappears, and we get:

$$\begin{aligned} & -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) e^{-1} e^{-\frac{i\Delta t (L'(\dot{x}_{\pm}))^2}{2\hbar L''(\dot{x}_{\pm})}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{2\hbar} L''(\dot{x}_{\pm}) \left(\varepsilon + \frac{L'(\dot{x}_{\pm})}{L''(\dot{x}_{\pm})}\right)^2} \\ &= -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) e^{-1} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{2\hbar} L''(\dot{x}_{\pm}) \varepsilon^2} \\ &= -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) e^{-1} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{i\Delta t}{2\hbar} 2m\varepsilon^2} \\ &= -\left(\frac{m}{2\pi i\hbar}\right) e^{-1} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\varepsilon e^{\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar} \varepsilon^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi\hbar\Delta t}} e^{-1} e^{i\pi/4} = \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi\hbar e^2 \Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} \quad (36) \end{aligned}$$

Here we clearly see how the physical effect of a complex-valued stationary path evolution manifests, in the real and negative exponent of the exponential: damping of the probability amplitude, indicating tunneling behavior. However, it was not yet addressed what it means for $L'(\dot{x}_{\pm})$ to be zero at \dot{x}_{\pm} . From (26) we see that:

$$\dot{x}_{\pm} = v \pm \sqrt{\frac{V}{m} + \frac{i\hbar}{m\Delta t} - v^2}$$

But for $L'(\dot{x}_{\pm}) = L'(v) = 0$ to hold, it must be that:

$$\sqrt{\frac{V}{m} + \frac{i\hbar}{m\Delta t} - v^2} = 0 \rightarrow \frac{V}{m} - v^2 = -\frac{i\hbar}{m\Delta t} \quad (37)$$

Substituting (37) in (34), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi\hbar\Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{-\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar}\left(\frac{V}{m}-v^2\right)} &= \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi\hbar\Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{-\frac{im\Delta t}{\hbar}\left(-\frac{i\hbar}{m\Delta t}\right)} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi\hbar\Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} e^{-1} = \sqrt{\frac{m}{4\pi\hbar e^2\Delta t}} e^{i\pi/4} \quad (38) \end{aligned}$$

This is consistent with (36). Restoring physical units and invoking the standard WKB (stationary-phase) result for a classically forbidden slice (Landau & Lifshitz, §53), the numerical damping exponent of minus one corresponds to the damping factor $\exp(-\kappa\Delta x)$, with $\kappa = \sqrt{2m(V-E)}/\hbar$, Δx the slice-length, and E the kinetic energy. Squaring the magnitude of contribution to total probability amplitude (38) from the first slice, and multiplying with the slice-length $(x_2 - x_0)$ gives the approximate probability of observing the particle in between x_0 and x_2 :

$$P(x_0, x_2) \approx \frac{m}{4\pi\hbar e^{2\kappa\Delta x}\Delta t} \cdot (x_2 - x_0) = \frac{m\Delta x}{2\pi\hbar e^{2\kappa\Delta x}2\Delta t} \quad (39)$$

This is nearly equal in form to that of the free particle (16) but damped, which is the type of behavior we would expect if an otherwise free particle has to tunnel through a constant potential. In the limit of $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, $P(x_0, x_0 + dx) \rightarrow \frac{p}{2\pi\hbar e^{2\kappa dx}}$ with p the momentum associated with the stationary-path evolution. Furthermore, the only way to obtain a physically meaningful solution, i.e. a damped probability amplitude due to the obstructing constant potential making the region in between x_0 and x_2 classically forbidden, seems to be by demanding that *both* factors of (23) are zero, so that $\dot{x} = v$ with $v = \pm \sqrt{\frac{V}{m} + \frac{i\hbar}{m\Delta t}}$.

Discussion

The analysis provided here should be viewed as *conceptually explorative and heuristic rather than strictly formal*. The analysis seeks to explore connections between stationary action, probability amplitude, integrating over *path evolutions*, and the semiclassical limit. It explores how variations of the path integral at the level of a single infinitesimal slice can yield meaningful insight into the behavior of quantum trajectories. A local variational analysis of the free particle and a particle near a constant potential provides insight into how the stationary-action principle underlies both classical and quantum behavior, through a local relationship between the classical slice-action and a functional over the phase-weighting of quantum path evolutions. In particular, this functional is proportional to the slice-action itself up to additive and multiplicative constants. This proportionality implies that the stationarity of this functional is equivalent to the stationarity of the slice-action, which in turn generates the semiclassical stationary path evolution. The resulting formulation produces results consistent with known short-time propagators for the free particle and a particle near a constant potential, including tunneling behavior.

Although the applied variational manipulations seem to form a consistent local framework, it must be emphasized that the employed analytical procedures are *heuristic* in nature. The Feynman path integral in real time is not a convergent functional integral; it is defined through a limiting process of recursive Gaussian integrations or, equivalently, by analytic continuation from imaginary time. Thus, the variational manipulations applied here do not constitute a formal derivation within a rigorously defined functional-analytic framework. Instead, they are a *local approximation argument* carried out at the level of a single infinitesimal time-slice, using standard physical reasoning about small variations and stationary phase. It seems interesting to note that merely expanding up to first order in the infinite Taylor-expansion of the phase-weighting exponential (7), is already sufficient to capture the physical behavior of a free particle, and that expanding up to second order seems to capture the full range of physical behavior of a particle near a constant potential. One might then wonder what all the other infinitely many terms may capture in terms of other physical behavior.

A reader might question the validity of applying the Euler–Lagrange procedure to quantities based on the path-integral integrand, given that the integrand is oscillatory and does not lend itself to the application of a variational functional in the conventional sense. However, the method used here only assumes the *local stationarity of the slice contribution*, which in the time-sliced formalism is an ordinary function of finite variables. The calculus of variations, when restricted to this small domain, operates purely algebraically and yields relations that seem to remain valid in the limit as $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, as formulations resulting from the procedure are consistent with known short-time propagators for the free particle and a particle near a constant potential, including tunneling behavior. Calculus of variations can therefore be applied to investigate how stationary paths arise locally, to complement conceptual understanding of how the stationary-action principle underlies both classical and quantum behavior.

Another potential concern is the treatment of *acceleration and velocity* within a slice. The present formulation explicitly assumes that for sufficiently small Δt , the motion over the slice can be taken as linear, so that \dot{x} is constant and $\ddot{x} = 0$ locally. This does not imply that the full quantum path is linear or unaccelerated; rather, the path integral sums over all sequences of such infinitesimal, constant-velocity segments. In the stationary-phase limit, the sequence of these locally linear pieces coalesces into the classical trajectory of uniform motion. Again, the local character of the variational analysis (in the limit as $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$) seems to yield meaningful Euler-Lagrange procedures, the validity of which in current form is likely to break down in a global framework of variational analysis.

A further subtlety lies in the treatment of complex-valued stationary trajectories when potentials are introduced. In this work, such solutions are interpreted as semiclassical tunneling paths, corresponding to deformations of the integration contour into regions where the action acquires an imaginary component. This interpretation is physically consistent with standard semiclassical treatments of tunneling, though it is not formulated here in the language of contour deformation or steepest-descent analysis (e.g., Berry & Mount). Such formal details, while necessary for a rigorous account, lie beyond the heuristic scope of the present argument.

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